

Agroforestry in Ireland

Stakeholders Policy challenges

- Full integration of agroforestry in other agricultural schemes
- Inventory of problems for each region and how was it solved
- Factsheets: current policy an AF at regional level
- Bureaucracy: management and processing usually at slow pace, administrative forms tedious.
- Permanent land use change
- Financial supports from state for too short a time period
- Legal framework non dynamic. Regulation non adapted to new productive and processing models.

Policy recommendations

- 1.- Development of working groups to fit funds to existing challenges, reduce bureaucracy at minimum and adapt the legal framework for agroforestry practices implementation in both forest and agricultural land uses.
- 2.- Develop advisory systems linked to global and local research.
- 3.- Establish a short, intermediate and long term strategy to ensure agroforestry transition based on knowledge and digitalization.
- 4.- Understanding agroforestry as a land management ecosystem services provider and a value chain promotion linked to the use of the territory.
- 5.- Better understanding between the different ministries (i.e. environment and agriculture).

STATE:	Ireland		Silvopasture	3,14%	6,75%
Nut level:	-		Agrisilviculture	0,00%	0,00%
Eurostat code:	IE		Agrosilvopasture	0,00%	0,00%
Area (km ²):	68.655		Kitchen gardens	0,02%	0,01%
Population	2018	2022	Holding type	2016	2023
Population	4.855.733	5.154.277	Natural person (ha)	4.847.060	3.983.710
Density (p km ⁻²)	71	75	Legal person (ha)	36.580	258.870
Cover data	2018	2022	Group holding and Common land unit (ha)	-	457.910
Forest	17,11%	9,60%	Natural person (holder)	137.140	117.170
Arable land	6,67%	8,40%	Legal person (holder)	430	2.960
Permanent crops	0,04%	0,06%	Group holding and Common land unit (holder)	-	7.930
Agroforestry	3,16%	6,76%	Regional Used Agricultural Area	2016	2023
Shrubland	5,77%	7,96%	Farm number	137.560	128.060
Grassland	54,03%	52,98%	Farm ha (UAA)	4.883.640	4.700.490
Agroforestry Practice Cover	2018	2022			

Animal populations (Thousand head) 2018 2023

Live bovine animals	6.593	6.526
Dairy cows	1.369	1.511
Non dairy cows	982	819
Live swine, domestic species	1.572	1.408
Live sheep	3.798	3.741
Live goats	-	-

CROPS (Hectares) 2016 2023

Utilised agricultural area	4.883.640	4.700.490
Cereals for the production of grain (including seed)	280.370	270.740
Common wheat and spelt	67.840	56.060
Durum wheat	-	-
Rye and winter cereal mixtures (maslin)	-	-
Barley	189.290	187.100
Oats and spring cereal mixtures	23.230	27.270
Grain maize and corn-cob-mix	-	-
Rice	-	-
Dry pulses and protein crops for the production of grain	12.470	16.890
Industrial crops	11.090	22.080
Cotton seed and fibre	-	-
Other oilseed crops n.e.c.	-	-
Fibre crops	-	-
Aromatic, medicinal and culinary plants	20	60

Plants harvested green from arable land	125.690	984.670
Green maize	10.940	19.660
Kitchen gardens	70	-

Rural Development Interventions promoting agroforestry

ENVCLIM(70) - Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments

Interventions	1
Forestry	1
Crop diversification including woody perennials	0
Crop rotation including woody perennials	1
Livestock including woody perennials	0
Woody perennials to reduce soil erosion	0
Woody perennials to add organic matter	0
Woody perennials to reduce soil chemical contamination	0
Animal welfare using woody perennials	0
Permanent Grasslands with woody perennials	0
Agroforestry on Permanent Crops	1
Interventions	1

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References

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